

Women Empowerment in Reality is Still a Dream - An Explorative Study

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Introduction

Empowerment is a process of awareness and conscientization, of capacity building leading to greater participation, effective decision-making power and control leading to transformative action. Empowerment is now increasingly seen as a process by which the one's without power gain greater control over their lives. This involves ability to get what one wants and to influence others on our concerns.

The Cairo conference in 1994 organized by UN on Population and Development called attention to women's empowerment as a central focus and UNDP developed the Gender Empowerment measure (GEM) which focuses on the three variables that reflect women's participation in society – political power or decision-making, education and health. 1995 UNDP report was devoted to women's empowerment and it declared that if human development is not engendered it is endangered a declaration which almost become a lei motif for further development measuring and policy planning.

Two perspectives have emerged in the contemporary discourse on the modalities of gender equity; women's development and women's empowerment. Human development report since 1999 demonstrate that practically no country in the world treats its women as well as men according to the measures of life expectancy wealth and education. Developing countries present especially urgent problems where caste and class result in acute failure of human capabilities of women.

The virtues of a measure such as the GDI, which can project the status of women by encapsulating achievements in three basis dimensions, soon become clear to policy makers. It spurred efforts to rank States in India by calculating their GDI (Shiv Kumar 1966, SeetaPrabhu, Sarkar and Radha 1996; Empowerment of women

is essentially the process of upliftment of economic, social and political status of women, the traditionally underprivileged ones, in the society. Women constitute approximately a half of every society and have a determining role in personal, family and social lives (AsadiAraghi, 2000).

Review of Literature

H. Subrahmanyam (2011) compares women education in India at present and Past. Author highlighted that there has a good progress in overall enrolment of girl students in schools. The term empower means to give lawful power or authority to act. It is the process of acquiring some activities of women.

M. BhavaniSankara Rao (2011) has highlighted that health of women members of SHG have certainly taken a turn to better. It clearly shows that health of women members discuss among themselves about health related problems of other members and their children and make them aware of various Government provisions specially meant for them.

Doepke M. Tertilt M. (2011) analysed in his study, Does Female Empowerment Promote Economic Development? This study is an empirical analysis suggesting that money in the hands of mothers benefits children. This study developed a series of non-cooperative family bargaining models to understand what kind of frictions can give rise to the observed empirical relationship.

Duflo E. (2011) Women's Empowerment and Economic Development, National Bureau of Economic Research Cambridge The study argues that the inter relationships of the Empowerment and Development are probably too weak to be self-sustaining and that continuous policy commitment to equality for its own sake may be needed to bring about equality between men and women.

Sethuraman K. (2008) The Role of Women's Empowerment and Domestic Violence in child Growth and under nutrition in a Tribal and Rural Community in South India. This research paper explores the relationship between Women's Empowerment and Domestic Violence, maternal nutritional status and the nutritional status and growth over six months in children aged 6 to 24 months in a rural and tribal community. This longitudinal observational study undertaken in rural Karnataka, India included tribal and rural subjects.

Venkata Ravi and Venkatraman (2005) focused on the effects of SHG on women participation and exercising control over decision making both in family matters and in group activities

Morrison and Von Glinow (1990) the study count factors such as the lack of chances of advancement for women in organization, the dominance of male managers in organizations, the lack of models of female managers in organizations, and the male feeling of racism as main barriers on the path of women in attaining management positions. In a study, between those managers who had been proposed to take the responsibility of all their tasks in their own authorities, about 20% of them took this responsibility and used it. About 50% of them cautiously tested the proposition and after 6 months, they started to it. An about 30% of them totally avoided to take the responsibility. Regarding the mentioned discussion, it can be said that one of the most important barriers of empowering in the three mentioned dimensions is the issue of managers' attitudes or approach.

Gill (1997), in a research titled as "women's ability via outlooks of Philipian women in a nongovernmental rural program" investigated the rural women's participation with low levels of income at the center of rural agricultural development. The study indicated that the mentioned program has made women reinforce and improve the conditions of their lives and families. This study referred to some gender issues and inequality in relation to intensity, work value, sharing situations, power and control of income of households which hinders women's complete participation in real development. In addition, unfair political, economic, and cultural structures causes gender roots and class limitations which per se prevent the realization of women's complete potentials in the process of development (Dehghanian, 2013).

Kung (1997), in a study, by reviewing women's freedom structure in Korea, declared employment and social activities of Korean women in 1996 as follows: 31.8% worked as employees, 13% as university professors, 7% as general managers, 3.6% as the crew, and 6.8% as the staff of productive units. Kung in his study stated the percentage of women's income compared to men's in terms of cases of the study, their age, and etc. implementing the policy of women's participation in the approval of general laws and the structure of social projects and political activities can be the requirement of women's empowerment (Taghizadeh, 2007)

Miller (1998) in his research concluded that discrimination and bias are two cultural dimensions which are located on the path of women's advancement in management. Bias means having negative attitudes towards a member of an organization due to his group identify and discrimination means observable behavior towards that person due to the same reason (Miller, 1998).

Cho (2003), in his thesis investigated the organizational culture and empowerment for changes in small productive industries in Hong Kong. The results of the study indicated that when management in organizational changes only considers hardware, it will face with failure because in organizational changes, software is a part of necessary parts. Organizational culture which guides the changes and empowerment of the staff is the main software part which conducts the successful process of changes. Research indicates that the mentioned software is the main core of successful implementation of changes in organizational culture for continuing quality improvement. The advantages of empowering the staff have been discussed and it is believed that by clarifying these chains of success in productive industries in Hong Kong will increase significantly (Ali Naghian, 2007).

“The UN in the Document of the General Assembly Special Session for Women counts the barriers of women's empowerment as cases such as the lack of education, extra loads burdened on women at work with wage and without it, attitudes and negative social clichés (the UN Document of the General Assembly Special Session for Women). In the UN document in Beijing, it is mentioned that educational courses and curriculum are greatly advocates a particular gender, and is rarely sensitive to women's and girl's needs. This issue reinforces the male and female roles and causes that the chance of full and equal participation be avoided from women in a society. The tutors' unawareness of affairs related to gender in all educational levels reinforces discriminative tendencies and removes respect for females. Therefore, it results the reinforcement of inequality available among women and men (Beijing action plan and declaration).

Rezazadeh (2011), in his study titled as “empowering women and appropriate urban governance in Iran” investigated the women's role in urban management and the possibility of more tendencies towards active participation of women in different fields. This study indicated that women are in search of getting power and taking more active roles in urban life. They have used all accessible resources for improving their own abilities. In addition, further research is required for better understanding of cultural and social barriers for increasing women's participation rate in governance (Rezazadeh, 2011).

Ezzedeen and Ritchey (2009) in their research titled as “professional advancement and family strategies of women's executive balance” investigated the professional advancement of women and the creation of balance between executive affairs and families, and guided women to pursue a balanced combination of professional and executive activities, families and organizations, and be committed to women's advancement (Ezzedeen and Ritchey, 2009).

Dehghanian et al., (2012), in their research investigated the factors limiting women in governmental organizations and concluded that structural, cultural, and social factors are among those limiting women in governmental agencies (Dehghanian et al., 2012).

Women's Empowerment Principles in Brief

1. Establish high-level corporate leadership for gender equality.
2. Treat all women and men fairly at work – respect and support human rights and nondiscrimination.
3. Ensure the health, safety and well-being of all women and men workers.
4. Promote education, training and professional development for women.
5. Implement enterprise development, supply chain and marketing practices that empower women.
6. Promote equality through community initiatives and advocacy.
7. Measure and publicly report on progress to achieve gender equality.

Theories Behind Empowerment

Empowerment Theory

Empowerment from Psychodynamic Approach

From psychodynamic approach, empowerment, in addition to increasing self-esteem, causes changes in a set of phenomena. It should be noted that conducting real empowerment requires understanding a set of mental differences and commitment of managers as well as employees constructed on the basis of integrity, honesty, and mutual trust (Taheri Tarigh, 2004). Changes in culture, behaviors, and old habits is a very appropriate method by which we can create a very powerful relationship between managers and the staff based on moral and ethical values. In addition, it should be tried that individuals feel freedom, respect, motivation, and authority and exemplify ethical values such as originality, trust, and confidence for themselves and their own organization (Ghasemi, 2003).

Empowerment from Ultra-Motivational Approach

Thomas and Velthouse in their interpretative model for intrinsic task motivation, define the task of empowerment as follows: Empowerment, empowering individuals, authority cession and capacity building. Empowerment is a title for the new paradigm of motivation which is necessary with the created changes of a search for proper alternatives for management forms motivating commitment, risk and innovation. The new paradigm includes simple controls and emphasis on internalized commitment in job themselves. Empowering is the process of developing culture and this development includes the following cases: Participation in information in the form of shared vision, clear objectives, decision making frameworks, and transparency of the results of efforts. Increasing competencies via learning and experiencing Obtaining benefits for doing tasks effectively Providing supports in the form of guiding and tutoring, cultural support and motivating risk appetite Individuals, when working, will be empowered by experiencing and learning, and this is an opportunity which an employer may provide for an employee. Empowerment is the process of becoming and this is a task not a result. Empowerment is a continuous improvement and never ends. An individual cannot become absolutely empowered and only in this case that empowerment becomes a part of organizational culture (Thomas and Velthouse, 1990: 666-681).

Empowerment form Relational (Multidimensional) Approach

In scientific resources related to this approach an up to bottom and mechanical definition is defined which indicates individuals' power and their absolute dependency in relation with others (Spreitzer, 1996). According to this approach, applying new processes and distributing power causes the empowerment of individuals. In fact, empowerment means delegating (legal and spiritual) authority and requires investigating the role of managers and leaders both before empowering and

after it because they have great and inevitable effects on the staff's psychological perception of empowerment, and play important and different roles such as creating shared objectives, promoting the staff's senses regarding their empowerments, emphasis on the staff's efforts and praising their roles in assisting to attain organizational objectives and concentrating strategies motivating group autonomy and independence in decision making (HorAbadiFarahani, 2005). From this approach, empowerment is a process through which a leader or manager tries to divide power among his subordinates.

Objectives

1. To assess the Awareness of Women Empowerment in India
2. To analyze the Factors influencing the Economic Empowerment of Women
3. To explore significant difference between gender and women empowerment
4. To determine the effect of education vs women empowerment

Methodology

The methodology employed in this special study is an exploratory research in addition, in terms of objectives.

Data Collection Instrument

There were various studies which were suitable for founding the theoretical framework of the present study. In addition, a questionnaire was used including

Data Analysis

Analysis means the computation of certain indices or measures along with searching for patterns of relationship that exist among the data groups. It helps in the testing of hypothesis for drawing inferences. So, data analysis is a crucial event in any research project because the inferences are made only based on the results of the analysis. After collecting data from, the questionnaires were checked for omissions and commissions to discard the incomplete ones. A total of 50 valid questionnaires were selected.

Number of Respondents	Received	Fully Filled	Percentage of Respondents
150	90	50	50%

Main Research Hypotheses

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant difference between gender and women empowerment.

Alternate Hypothesis (H1): There is a significant difference between gender and women empowerment.

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant difference between education vs women empowerment

Alternate Hypothesis (H2): There is a significant difference between education vs women empowerment

One Way Anova Test-1

Significant difference between gender with respect to women empowerment

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant difference between gender and women empowerment.

Alternate Hypothesis (H1): There is a significant difference between gender and women empowerment.

**Table 1
Gender**

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	7.745	4	1.936	46.470	0.000
Within Groups	1.875	45	0.042		
Total	9.620	49			

Calculated F value = 46.470

Degree of Freedom = 4, 45

Level of Significance = 5 percentage

Tabulated F value = 2.588

Calculated value > Tabulated value

Inference

Null Hypothesis is rejected

Alternative hypothesis is accepted at 5 percentage level of significance.

There is a significant difference between gender and women empowerment

One Way Anova Test-2

Significant difference between education vs women empowerment

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant difference between education vs women empowerment

Alternate Hypothesis (H2): There is a significant difference between education vs women empowerment

Table 2

Age group	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	28.203	4	7.051	6.638	0.000
Within Groups	47.797	45	1.062		
Total	76.000	49			

Calculated F value = 6.638

Degree of Freedom = 4, 45

Level of Significance = 5 percentage

Tabulated F value = 2.588

Calculated value > Tabulated value

Inference

Null Hypothesis is rejected

Alternative hypothesis is accepted at 5 percentage level of significance

There is a significant difference between education vs women empowerment

Percentage Analysis

Table 3 The Table Shows Women Need for Empowerment

Particular	No of respondents	Percentage percentage
Decision Making Power	5	10 percentage
Access to Employment	11	22 percentage
Access to Education	22	44 percentage
Domestic Violence	9	18 percentage
Exposure to Media	3	6 percentage
Total	50	100 percentage

Chart 1 The Chart Shows the Need for Women Empowerment

Inference

It is concluded that 44 percentage of the women expect access to Education for empowerment, 22 percentage of the women expects access to Employment for empowerment, 10 percentage of the women expects decision making power for empowerment, 18 percentage of the women experience Domestic Violence for empowerment 6 percentage of the women expects Exposure to Media for empowerment.

Table 4 The Table Shows the Hinderance to Women Empowerment

Particular	No of respondents	Percentage percentage
Low ability to bear Risk	29	58 percentage
Gender discrimination	15	30 percentage
Low need for achievement	4	8 percentage
Lack of Education	2	4 percentage
Total	50	100 percentage

Chart 2 The Chart Shows the Hinderance to Women Empowerment

Inference: It is concluded that 58percentage of women have hindrance of low ability to bear risk, 30 percentage of the women state Gender discrimination among the people is a hindrance, 8 percentageof the women state low need for achievementis a hindrance, 4 percentageof the women state lack of Educationis a hindrance.

Findings

- There is a significant difference between education vs women empowerment
- There is a significant difference between gender and women empowerment
- TheHindrance to women empowerment islow ability to bear risk, gender discrimination, low need for achievement, lack of education.

Suggestion

Awareness programmes need to be organized for creating awareness among women especially belonging to weaker sections about their rights.

Society must take initiative to create a climate in which there is no gender discrimination and women have full opportunities of self-decision making and participating in social, political and economic life of the country with a sense of equality.

It is essential as their thought and their value systems lead the development of a good family, good society and ultimately a good nation. The best way of empowerment is perhaps through inducting women in the mainstream of development. Women empowerment will be real and effective only when they are endowed income and property so that they may stand on their feet and build up their identity in the society.

Women should be allowed to work and should be provided enough safety and support to work. They should be provided with proper wages and work at par with men so that their status can be elevated in the society.

Challenges

Education: While the country has grown from leaps and bounds since independence where education is concerned. the gap between women and men is severe. While 82.14% of adult men are educated, only 65.46% of adult women are known to be literate in India. The gender bias is in higher education, specialized professional trainings which hit women very hard in employment and attaining top leadership in any field.

Poverty: Poverty is considered the greatest threat to peace in the world, and eradication of poverty should be a national goal as important as the eradication of illiteracy. Due to this, women are exploited as domestic helps

Health and Safety: The health and safety concerns of women are paramount for the wellbeing of a country and is an important factor in gauging the empowerment of women in a country. However there are alarming concerns where maternal healthcare is concerned.

Professional Inequality: This inequality is practiced in employment sand promotions. Women face countless handicaps in male customized and dominated environs in Government Offices and Private enterprises.

Morality and Inequality: Due to gender bias in health and nutrition there is unusually high morality rate in women reducing their population further especially in Asia, Africa and china.

Household Inequality: Household relations show gender bias in infinitesimally small but significant manners all across the globe, more so, in India e.g. sharing burden of housework, childcare and menial works by so called division of work.

Ways to Empower Women Changes in Women's Mobility and Social Interaction

Changes in women's labor patterns

Changes in women's access to and control over resources and

Changes in women's control over Decision making providing education

Self employment and Self help group

Providing minimum needs like Nutrition, Health, Sanitation, Housing

Other than this society should change the mentality towards the word women

Encouraging women to develop in their fields they are good at and make a career

Conclusion

With considering the theories and all the studies conducted in the literature related to the subject, the theoretical framework of the research. It is evidenced in many studies level of awareness of government schemes is very low so more effective publicity is necessary. A more effective MIS system for monitoring women welfare, women empowerment programmes is to be developed which is simple, transparent and involves both government and non government functionaries. Gender resource center with autonomy need to be established in all states and in case of larger states there must be more than one such center involving academic & activities. The verbal change from women welfare to women rights needs to be converted into reality. The questions surrounding women's empowerment the condition and position of women have now become critical to the human rights based approaches to development.

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